

Evaluation of antibacterial potentialities of *Terminalia arjuna* wight & arn leaf gall: an ethnomedicinal plant

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ABSTRACT

In the current exploration an attempt has been made to assess the antibacterial potentialities of *Terminalia arjuna* Wight and Arn leaf galls. It belongs to the family Combretaceae commonly known as 'Arjuna', an important ethno medicinal plant. The different solvent extract of *T. arjuna* leaf gall were subjected to antibacterial activity, total phenol and total carbohydrate content estimation. The antimicrobial susceptibility was screened by means of well diffusion, disc diffusion, MIC and MBC methods. The result showed that the methanol extract was active against both gram negative and gram positive bacteria, when compared to other solvent extracts. The methanol extract of leaf gall showed optimum activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC-7903), *Enterobacter aerogenes* (MTCC-7325), *Enterococcus faecalis* (MTCC – 6845) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC- 3160). The highest amount of phenolic content was observed in methanol extract (93.62 µg GAE/mg of extract) followed by acetone >water >chloroform. The highest value of carbohydrate were observed in water extract (80.90 µg/mg of extract) followed by >acetone > methanol > chloroform. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report of exploiting the antimicrobial properties of leaf gall of *Terminalia arjuna*. Our results indicated that the *Terminalia arjuna* leaf gall possess potential antibacterial activity.

Keywords: *T. arjuna*, Methanol extract, Antibacterial activity.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants are one of the oldest existing complete medical practices in the world. Natural plant products are important resources for biologically active drugs (Saleh et al., 2009). The higher plants have the ability to produce different types of organic compounds, which are used for self defense are referred as secondary metabolites (Evan et al., 1986).

There has been a growing interest in the study of medicinal plants as natural products in different parts of the globe (Gazzaneo et al., 2005). Medicinal plants possess active chemical ingredients with high antioxidant potentiality play an important role in the control of different

forms of diseases (Lukmanul et al., 2008), and have possible benefits to the society. WHO reported that more than 80% of population depends on plant based products to meet their health demands (Ramya et al., 2008). In 21st century bacterial infection is one of the most important global health issue (Moris et al., 2002). With the development and rapid spread of multidrug resistant pathogens antimicrobial chemotherapy was severely affected. In recent years, multiple drug resistance in both plant and human pathogens has been developed due to indiscriminate use of synthetic drugs (Hart and Karriuri, 1998). Therefore a broad spectrum antibacterial agent is needed right away to fight the diminishing effectiveness of antibiotics (Chopra et al., 1997).

To overcome these problems it is necessary to develop new antibiotic with novel mechanism of action (Wang et al., 2003). The natural products of higher plants may possess a new source of antimicrobial agents with possibly novel mechanism of action (Ahamed and Aquil 2007). The plants are very effective in the treatment of infectious diseases, while simultaneously mitigating many of the side effects that are often associated with synthetic antimicrobials (Iwan et al., 1999). Therefore it is often great importance to carry out screening of the plants in order to validate for using as folk medicine (Tomoko et al., 2002).

Terminalia arjuna Wight & Arn., it belongs to the family Combretaceae commonly known as 'Arjuna' is a large deciduous tree commonly present throughout India. It is traditionally used in the control of myocardial infarction, acute pancreatitis, cardiovascular diseases, atherosclerosis, inflammatory bowel disease, amyloidosis diabetes, senile dementia, retinal degeneration and arthritis (Dodia, 2004). In Indian system of medicine owes its origin (Dwivedi and Chaturvedi, 2000). *Terminalia arjuna* is a good hypolipidemic, anticoagulant, antihypertensive antithrombotic, antiviral, antifungal and antibacterial agent. Various phyto constituents have been isolated from *Terminalia arjuna* which includes triterpenoids having cardiovascular properties, flavonoids and tannins for having anticancer properties (warrier et al., 1996).

However, there are very limited reports concurrently on antagonistic activity of *Terminalia arjuna* leaf gall which is an important medicinal plant. With this background the present investigation was undertaken.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of *Terminalia arjuna* leaf gall samples

The leaf gall samples from the plant *Terminalia arjuna* were collected in and around University campus, Mysore during November 2013. The samples were brought to the laboratory for further process.

Extraction of compound

Leaf gall samples were shade dried and extraction was done by using soxhlet apparatus with solvent system (methanol, chloroform, ethyl acetate, water). The solvent extract was tested for screening of antimicrobial activity and desired solvent system was chosen for the conformation of antimicrobial activity.

Determination of total phenolic contents

Spectrophotometric assay was used to estimate the total phenolics in the crude extract following the method of Barreira et al., (2008). In brief 1mL of sample (1mg/mL) was mixed with 1mL of FC phenol reagent. Allow for three min and then 1mL of saturated sodium carbonate solution was added to the mixture and made up the volume to 10 mL with distilled water. Incubate for 90min in the dark, later the absorbance was measured at 725 nm. Gallic acid was used as standard and positive control.

Estimation of total carbohydrate

Total carbohydrate content was estimated by the method of Hedge and Hofreiter (1962). This compound forms with anthrone a green coloured product with an absorption maximum at 630nm. Glucose was used as a standard curve and the results were expressed as μg of glucose equivalents to per mg of extract.

Test microorganism

Both gram positive and gram negative bacteria were employed for the study of antibacterial spectrum of the extract. The bacteria includes *Staphylococcus aureus*, (MTCC-3160), *E. coli*, (MTCC - 7410), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC-7903), *Enterobacter aerogenes* (MTCC-7325), *Enterococcus faecalis* (MTCC - 6845) and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (MTCC - 7407) were obtained from MTCC Chandigarh, India.

Screening of antimicrobial activity

Well diffusion assay

The test pathogens were grown in 100mL of Muller hinton broth (Hi-Media) and incubated at 37° C for 24 hrs. The sterile petriplates were poured with molten Muller hinton agar and allowed to solidify. Sterile cork borer (5mm) was used to punch the wells. The fresh pathogen

cultures (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) were swabbed using a sterile cotton swab. The crude solvent extract of volume 50 μL was added in to the wells and allowed to diffuse. Equal volume of respective solvents was used as negative control and (Streptomycin) standard antibiotic is used as positive control. The inoculated plates were incubated at 37° C for 24 hours and the zone of inhibition was observed (Valgas et al., 2007).

Disc diffusion assay

The sterile disc of 3mm diameter was placed on the pre swabbed Muller hinton agar plates with bacterial strains (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*). The sample of volume 10 μL , 20 μL , 30 μL and 40 μL was inoculated on the impregnated sterile disc.

Incubated the plates at 37° C for 24 h and observe the zone of inhibition. Equal volume of respective solvent was used as negative control and (Streptomycin) standard antibiotic disc was used as positive control and inhibition zone was observed (Bhalodia and Shukla 2011).

Minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the compound

MIC of the compound was determined in a 96 well microtitre plate using broth dilution and plating technique (Viswanathan et al., 2014). MIC was calculated as minimum concentration of compound that showed a visible zone of inhibition of the indicator bacterial strain by reducing the viable cell number.

Minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of the compound

The crude solvent extract was further analyzed for Minimum bactericidal concentration (Dulger and Aki 2009) for the determination of bactericidal effect. The minimum concentration of the compound at which the indicator bacterial strains (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) were suppressed and it was

considered as Minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC).

RESULTS

Total phenolic content

The total phenolic content in *T. arjuna* leaf gall was determined as Gallic Acid Equivalent (GAE). A considerable amount of phenolic content was observed in methanol extract (93.62 μg GAE/mg of extract). The subsequent values were recorded by acetone (85.24 μg GAE/mg), water (83.25 μg GAE/mg) followed by chloroform (41.10 μg GAE/mg) extracts (Table 1).

Table1. Estimation of Total Phenols and Carbohydrates.

Total Phenols ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ of the extract)			
Chloroform Extract	Acetone Extract	Methanol Extract	Water Extract
41.40	85.24	93.62	83.25
Total Carbohydrate ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ of the extract)			
34.67	80.73	76.04	89.90

Total carbohydrate content

The maximum amount of total carbohydrate was recorded in the water extract (89.90 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ of the extract) followed by acetone extract (80.73 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ of the extract), methanol (76.04 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ of the extract) and chloroform (34.67 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ of the extract) (Table-1).

Antimicrobial activity

The results indicated that methanol extract of *T. arjuna* leaf gall exhibited maximum antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC-7903), *Enterobacter aerogenes* (MTCC-7325), *Enterococcus faecalis* (MTCC – 6845) with 75% zone of inhibition, when compare to standard antibiotic (Table. 2). The least activity was showed against *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with inhibition zone of 8mm. However the chloroform, ethylacetate and water extract showed moderate activity against *Enterococcus faecalis* (13.2 mm), *Escherichia coli* (10.6 mm) and *Enterobacter aerogenes* (14.8 mm) indicator strains compared to standard antibiotic.

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of different solvent extracts against pathogenic bacteria.

Antimicrobial activity ^a					
<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>
Chloroform extract					
8.9 ± 1.3	11.4 ± 1.1	10.1 ± 0.9	11.4 ± 2.4	13.2 ± 1.4	12.6 ± 1.6
Methanol extract					
11.2 ± 1.5	14.5 ± 1.7	16.2 ± 1.2	12.4 ± 1.2	16.4 ± 2.1	16.3 ± 2.4
Ethyl acetate extract					
10.6 ± 2.4	8.1 ± 4.6	8.5 ± 1.1	8.2 ± 1.1	9.4 ± 1.0	12 ± 0.6
Water extract					
10.1 ± 1.6	12.1 ± 2.0	13.7 ± 0.6	12.4 ± 1.3	14.8 ± 1.8	14.1 ± 1.2
Standard Antibiotic					
22.5 ± 1.8	20.2 ± 2.2	23.2 ± 1.4	20.6 ± 1.6	22.5 ± 1.8	21.5 ± 1.2

^aZone of inhibition in mm a=Mean ± SE, (n=3).

Table 3. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) µg/mL.

<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
Chloroform Extract (mg/ml)					
3.5	3.5	3.0	4.0	3.5	3.0
Acetone Extract (mg/ml)					
4.0	3.5	3.0	3.5	3.0	4.0
Methanol Extract (mg/ml)					
2.5	2.0	2.0	2.5	2.0	3.0
Water Extract (mg/ml)					
4.0	4.5	3.5	4.5	4.0	4.5

Table 4. Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) µg/mL.

<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
Chloroform Extract (mg/ml)					
5.0	5.5	5.0	5.5	6.5	6.0
Acetone Extract (mg/ml)					
6.0	6.5	6.0	6.5	6.0	5.5
Methanol Extract (mg/ml)					
4.5	4.0	4.0	4.5	4.0	4.0
Water Extract (mg/ml)					
6.0	7.5	7.5	6.5	7.0	6.5

MIC (Minimal inhibitory concentration)

The MIC values of different solvent extracts were represented in table 3. Methanol extract is very significant with 2mg/ml of MIC similarly the MIC values were significantly high against these pathogens. However the pathogens *E. coli* showed intermediate sensitivity to the methanol extract of *T. arjuna* leaf gall. Remaining solvent extracts showed moderate activity against all indicator strains.

MBC (Minimum bactericidal concentration)

MBC indicates the ability of the antimicrobial compound to suppress viable bacterial pathogens. The methanol extract of *T. arjuna* leaf gall showed MBC values of 4mg/ml showing maximum inhibition ability to all the bacterial strains (Table. 4). The water extract showed maximum MBC values i.e. 7.5 mg/ml with least inhibition to almost all the pathogens. However the chloroform and acetone extract showed moderate MBC values against all the indicator strains. The maximum MBC value was observed for *S. aureus* (7.5 mg/ml) and

Klebsiella pneumoniae (7.5 mg/ml) with water extracts. Whereas the least MBC values were observed for *S. aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Enterobacter aerogenes* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with 4.0 µg/ml with methanol extract. Remaining all the strains was moderately susceptible.

DISCUSSION

The antibacterial and some biochemical screening test revealed the potential effects of extract in bacteria. As represented in the results the methanol extract is much more effective compared to other extracts. Phenolic compounds generally occurring groups of phytochemicals, are of substantial interest as they are reported to show signs of anti-allergenic, anti-atherogenic, anti-thrombotic, cardioprotective and vasodilator effects (Lazos et al., 2011). Plant phenolic compounds are major bioactive substances involved in antioxidant activity by eliminating the free radicals and also responsible for antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancerous and antimicrobial activities (Yang et al., 2013). From the current exploration it can be observed that methanol extract exhibited higher content of phenol (93.62 µg /mg. Free radicals play an important role in the degenerative diseases (Chin-Yuan et al., 2007). Such material when inspired as a part of the diet will fundamentally contribute in cell endorsement in opposition to harmful action of reactive oxygen species, mainly oxygen free radicals fashioned in response to mineral nutrient deficiency.

The total carbohydrates attributes the nutritional worth of *T. arjuna* leaf galls which gives hold up to the phenolic content, bearing in mind the quantity of phenol is also dependable for estimations interrelated with antioxidant activity. Higher the phenolic content showed more antioxidant activity. Similar results were reported by Kathirvel and Sujatha, 2012 where they analyzed the *invitro* assessment of antioxidant and antibacterial properties of *Terminalia chebula* leaves, reported that water extract of leaf showed a maximum amount (101.9 µg) of carbohydrate. The basic units of carbohydrates are the monosaccharides, which

cannot be split by hydrolysis into simpler sugars. The carbohydrate content can be measured by hydrolyzing the polysaccharides into simple sugars by acid hydrolysis. Carbohydrates are first hydrolyzed into simple sugars using dilute hydrochloric acid. In hot acidic medium glucose is dehydrated to hydroxymethyl furfural. Carbohydrates are water soluble, therefore extracted efficiently in water and thus provided high significant amount of carbohydrate in water extract.

The antibacterial activity of different solvent extracts of *T. arjuna* has been represented in table 1, 2 and 3. The activity was performed on both gram positive and gram negative bacteria that have a significant role with regard to human health. Among all the solvents tested the methanol extract of *T. arjuna* leaf gall showed maximum antibacterial activity and showed least MIC value (2.0) and MBC values (4.0) that indicate the compound with better antagonistic activity. Similar results were reported by Naqvi et al., 2010 where the crude extract of *Terminalia chebula* showed more than 75% of inhibitory response in ethanolic extract against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*. Mathekga et al., 2000 reported that *Bacillus* species are common microbes found in diverse habitats, among those *Pseudomonas* species was clinically important as it causes some of the dreadful diseases such as mastitis, which is often difficult to diagnose (Salie et al., 1996). In the present study antagonistic activity was noticed against *P. aeruginosa* and *K. pneumoniae* which is on contrary to the results of Naqvi et al., 2010 which showed no sign of inhibition against *K. pneumoniae*.

Different human pathogenic bacteria *viz.* *E. coli*, *Klebsiella* are widely distributed nosocomial infections and thus creating a serious therapeutic problem (Akram et al., 2007). Our results are in line of earlier reports of Emran et al., 2011 who investigated the antibacterial activity of ethanolic leaf and fruit extract of *T. arjuna* showed antimicrobial activity against gram positive and gram negative bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The MIC value of the

present study (2mg/ml) was very significant when compare to previous reports (Ramya et al., 2008) where the MIC value of *T. arjuna* ethanolic leaf and fruit extract was 8mg/ml that is extensively high supporting the present study. Of all the solvents examined for the antimicrobial activity, the methanol extract of leaf gall of *T. arjuna* showed maximum antagonistic activity and this can be recommended for further studies.

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